

**THE EXTENT OF THE HUMAN RESOURCES INFORMATION SYSTEMS
USE - ANALYSIS IN ENTERPRISES IN SLOVAKIA**

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***Abstract.** Over time, personnel work has evolved from personnel administration to the strategic position of human resource management. Currently, we are experiencing an overload of information, as it is all around us. Information and data are very important for the enterprises. Information and data must be collected not only for legislative reasons, but also to ensure and increase its performance. For that reason, information systems are an integral part of enterprises, saving time and costs. The gradual transition from supporting administrative activities to management activities also meant highlighting the importance of information necessary for human resources management. Just as various areas and tasks of human resource management are part of human resource management in an organization, personnel information systems are becoming an*

integral part of management. The reliability of information, which is the basis for decision-making regarding measures in human resources management, is becoming increasingly important. The paper presents the results of the analysis of the use of human resources information systems in industrial enterprises in Slovakia. The authors of the article chose a questionnaire as a research tool. Overall, 288 respondents from industrial enterprises of various sizes in Slovakia took part in the research. The collected data were evaluated through descriptive statistics. The results of the presented research showed that information technologies facilitate not only everyday life and work across industries, but also penetrate into partial areas of human resource management. The results of the research assume other research tendencies and spaces for discussion, which include the interconnection of the used information systems with information systems in the field of human resources management, duplication in data entry, and the acceptance of technologies by employees is an integral part.

Keywords: *human resource information systems, human resource management, industrial enterprises, employees, development*

Introduction

Despite the significant gradual development of managerial decision-making, information continues to be a key aspect of such decision-making. Information provides structure, intensity and certainty to the decision-making process. Thus, information systems gain importance in supporting and supplementing managerial decisions in contemporary organizations [1]. Human resource information systems (HRIS) is defined as an information system that is aimed at supporting human resource management (HRM) functions and activities, as well as broader organizational processes aimed at managing human resources. A more formal definition of an HRIS is a system used to collect, store, manipulate, analyse, retrieve and distribute information related to an organization's human resources to support HRM and management decisions [2]. An information system is expected to produce

complete, accurate, accessible, timely, consistent and clear data to aid meaningful decision-making. Unnecessary information complicates the decision-making process and should be avoided. HRIS helps not only in storing information about employees in its database, but also helps in managing almost all HRM functions [3,4]. An HRIS does not have to be explicitly a computerized system. HRIS may also include information stored in paper form. For computer and especially HRIS software support, one of the main purposes of HRIS implementation is to reduce the amount of time that human resources (HR) personnel must spend on personnel administration and record keeping activities, and to devote more time to planning, recruiting, training, or change management, and innovation management. These arguments are among the main justifications for a computerized system [2,5].

Therefore, the main aim of the paper is to present the results of the analysis of the use of human resources information systems in industrial enterprises in Slovakia.

Methods and Results

As part of formulating the research area, we set the main goal of the research, which was to analyse the extent (the scope) of the use of HR information systems in industrial enterprises in Slovakia. Along with the development of personnel work, the way of using human resources information systems is changing. With the advent of digitization and automation, there is a digitalization of human resource management activities. In the research, we focused on the form in which information representing the content of HR information systems is obtained, processed and used.

For the purposes of the research, three research questions were formulated:

Research question 1 (RQ1): How did the employees of the enterprises applied their current employment?

Research question 2 (RQ2): How is employee attendance recorded in enterprises in Slovakia?

Research question 3 (RQ3): How are data transmitted and information obtained in partial areas of human resource management?

The chosen research tool was a questionnaire that was distributed to enterprises of various sizes. In total, respondents from 288 enterprises took part in the research. Respondents from large enterprises (250 or more employees) were most represented, which represents a total number of 169 respondents (58.68%), followed by respondents from medium-sized enterprises (50-250 employees), of which there were 66 (22.92%), then respondents from small enterprises (10-49 employees), of which there were 35 (12.15%) and the smallest part was represented by respondents from micro enterprises (up to 10 employees), of which there were 18 (6.25%).

Considering that the intention of the authors of the paper was to capture the answers of a wider range of HRIS users, research was focused on employees in various job positions. The distribution of respondents based on the representation of their job positions is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Representation of respondents based on their job positions (own elaboration, 2022)

Item	Absolute frequency	Relative frequency [%]
Manufacturing employee	61	21.18
Administrative employee	91	31.60
Specialist employee	100	34.72
Manager - management employee	36	12.50
No answer	0	0
Σ Sum	288	100.00

From the data in Table 1, it follows that employees in specialist positions were most represented, followed by respondents in administrative positions, and smaller groups of respondents were represented by manufacturing employees and managers.

After analysing the research sample, the authors of the paper proceeded to evaluate the first research question.

RQ1: How did the employees of the enterprises learn about the possibility of their current employment?

When evaluating the first research question, the authors of the paper focused on the way how employees of organizations in Slovakia applied for a current job. The evaluation of the research question is shown through descriptive statistics in Table 2.

Table 2. Method of applying for current employment (own elaboration, 2022)

Item	Absolute frequency	Relative frequency [%]
The employer own online application	17	05.90
The internet advertising (Profesia, LinkedIn ...)	114	39.59
E-mail	35	12.15
In writing by post	17	5.90
Personally	93	32.29
Other answer	12	4.17
Σ Sum	288	100.00

As can be seen in Table 2, in addition to the options offered, the respondents also chose the option of other answer, while among the free answers there were options such as recruitment through an agency, by recommendation, through informal personal contacts, through acquaintances, or based on phone calls.

Subsequently, the authors of the paper proceeded to evaluate the second research question.

RQ2: How is employee attendance recorded in enterprises in Slovakia?

The purpose of the research question was to find out whether employers in Slovakia mainly use electronic systems for attendance records, e.g. in the form of an identification (ID) card, chip, etc. The responses of the respondents are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Use of electronic attendance record systems (own elaboration, 2022)

Item	Absolute frequency	Relative frequency [%]
Yes	229	79.51
Partially / Sometimes	23	07.99
No	33	11.46
I do not know	3	01.04
Other answer	0	0
Σ Sum	288	100.00

As can be clearly seen from Table 3, electronic attendance record systems prevail among employers in Slovakia. From a practical point of view, however, it is important to be aware of the difference between working time records and attendance records. These terms are often incorrectly confused at work. The term attendance record refers to the employee's presence at the workplace and may not be consistent with his work performance. Pursuant to § 99 of the Labour Code, the employer is obliged to record the beginning and end of the time period in which the employee performed the work [6]. It is up to the voluntary choice of the employer which method of recording working time he chooses.

When evaluating the third research question, the authors of the paper focused on selected areas of human resource management.

RQ3: How are data transmitted and information obtained in partial areas of human resource management?

The results of the evaluation of research question 3 are shown using descriptive statistics in Tables 4 and 5. Table 4 shows the answers of the respondents regarding the transfer of information from selected areas of HRM in absolute frequency (AF) and relative frequency (RF).

Table 4. Method of transmitting information from selected areas of HRM regarding employee performance in absolute frequency (AF) and relative frequency (RF) (own elaboration, 2022)

The method used	Attendance		Work tasks		Work performances		Reasons for absence		Employee evaluation	
	AF	RF (%)	AF	RF (%)	AF	RF (%)	AF	RF (%)	AF	RF (%)
In written form	28	9.72	50	17.36	50	17.36	86	29.86	54	18.75
Electronically	232	80.56	164	56.94	161	55.90	148	51.39	134	46.53
Another form	10	3.47	70	24.31	33	11.46	46	15.97	80	27.78
No way	17	5.90	4	1.39	44	15.28	8	2.78	20	6.94
No answer	1	0.35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Σ Sum	288	100	288	100	288	100	288	100	288	100

As shown in Table 4, the electronic form of registration prevails in the registration of attendance and registration of work tasks. At least the electronic form of records is used in the evaluation of the employee. An important issue here is the use of employee evaluation when assigning work tasks, compatibility and coordination of related decisions.

Subsequently, the authors of the paper evaluated the respondents' answers to the transmission of information regarding changes and development possibilities in the organization. The answers are shown in Tables 6 and 7. Table 5 shows the answers of the respondents regarding the transfer of information from selected areas of HRM in absolute frequency (AF) and relative frequency (RF).

Table 5. Method of transmitting information from selected areas of HRM regarding changes and development opportunities in the organization in absolute frequency (AF) and relative frequency (RF) (own elaboration, 2022)

The method used	Education requirements		Suggestions for improvements		Information about the employee		Job offers in the enterprise		News in the enterprise		Current changes	
	AF	RF (%)	AF	RF (%)	AF	RF (%)	A F	RF (%)	A F	RF (%)	A F	RF (%)
In written form	48	16.67	62	21.53	90	31.25	35	12.15	37	12.85	34	11.81
Electronically	162	56.25	151	52.43	137	47.57	200	69.45	209	72.56	209	72.57
Another form	41	14.24	47	16.32	50	17.36	28	9.72	37	12.85	43	14.93
No way	37	12.84	28	9.72	11	3.82	25	8.68	5	1.74	2	0.69
No answer	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Σ Sum	288	100	288	100	288	100	288	100	288	100	288	100

As can be seen from the data shown in Table 5, it follows that current changes, news in the company and new job offers are most often processed electronically. Information about the employee, i.e. changes regarding employees such as marital status, health insurance company, etc. are most often processed in other ways.

Discussion and conclusion

The results of the presented research show that the electronicization of HRIS is an unstoppable trend, while the introduction of digital tools is the key to successful

business in a modern information environment [7]. HRIS implementation brings many solutions and simplifications of operational work with human resources. On the other hand, it brings several questions and areas of improvement. The first area is the complementarity of HRIS with existing and used corporate information systems. Enterprises usually use different business information systems or management systems that are focused on partial functional areas. Thus, their compatibility or duplication when entering data becomes a challenge for the management of enterprises. The question of security when processing sensitive data about employees is also a non-negligible issue. Information technologies that enable easier processing and manipulation of personal data are interconnected with questions of protecting this data from misuse [8]. Another challenge is the area of technology acceptance. Many employees have difficulty accepting new technologies and learning to work with them. As the results of the already presented study showed, the information system of human resources really changed gradually. The human resource information system affects the work activities of employees to such an extent that it has become an essential priority for organizations to maintain the quality of HRIS [9]. Acceptance conditions for the adaptation of new technologies and factors affecting employee satisfaction with the systems used therefore become an important research area.

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